

BIOcean5D

**MARINE BIODIVERSITY ASSESSMENT AND
PREDICTION ACROSS SPATIAL, TEMPORAL
AND HUMAN SCALES**

D1.3 Standardized sequencing and imaging data

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Author(s) and Affiliations	Julie Poulain (CEA), Paola Bertucci (EMBL), Fabien Lombard (SU), Marion Vilain (LOV), Victoria Bancel (LOV), Manoela Brandão (IMEV), Laëtitia Jalabert (IMEV), Marc Picheral (IMEV), Emmanuelle Martins (IMEV), Sophie Marro (LOV), Tina Wiegand (EMBL), Marta Rubio (EMBL)
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List of Acronyms

BID – Barcoded Identifiers
CEA- Commissariat a l'energie atomique et aux energies alternatives
COI – Cytochrome C Oxydase I
CNRS – Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique
DNA – deoxyribonucleic acid
DOC – dissolved organic carbon
ENA – European Nucleotide Archive
EMBL – European Molecular Biology Laboratory
EMBRC – European Marine Biological Resource Centre-ERIC
EtOH – Ethanol
eDNA – environmental DNA / Environmental deoxyribonucleic acid
ETH – Eidgenoessische Technische Hochschule Zuerich
FC – flow cytometry
GPS – Global Positioning System
MetaB- Metabarcoding
MetaG- Metagenomics
MetaT- Metatranscriptomics
PIQv – Quantitative Imaging Platform of Villefranche
QC – quality control
SOPs – Standard Operating Procedures
SU – Sorbonne University
TREC – TRaversing European Coastlines
WP - Work Package

Executive summary

D1.3 summarises the sequencing and imaging datasets produced in BIOcean5D, covering approximately 70,000 water, plankton and sediment samples from 115 land-to-sea transects (T1.1), more than 10,000 sediment samples from 15 historical sediment cores (T1.2), and plankton time series collected at multiple sites to study decadal changes (T1.3 and T1.4). It integrates outputs from multiple partner laboratories using standardised methods, including metabarcoding, metatranscriptomic and metagenomic sequences (T1.6.1), quantitative imaging methods (T1.6.2) as well as organismal and subcellular imaging (T1.6.3) data from TREC (Tara Europa) activities and other workflows. All data were generated under harmonised procedures to ensure cross-comparability, high-quality metadata, and readiness for integration into the BIOcean5D data hub with submission of sequences to the European Nucleotide Archive (ENA). This deliverable provides a comprehensive set of multi-omic and imaging data resources to support future analyses, modelling and cross-disciplinary research across the project.

Introduction

D1.3 documents the production, standardisation and preparation for integration of sequencing and imaging data within BIOcean5D. This project relies on diverse sample types such as water, sediments, meiofauna, etc., collected across work packages 1 and 5 (WPs) during the TREC-Tara Europa expeditions. These consistent procedures across laboratories ensured cross-site comparability.

The data were generated across multiple partner laboratories using shared protocols for genomic and imaging data production.

This deliverable is structured into three main parts reflecting the technological pillars of WP1:

- **Part A – Genomic Data:** Covers standardised procedures for nucleic acid extraction, library preparation, sequencing, data processing and submission practices.
- **Part B – Quantitative Imaging Data:** Details field protocols, acquisition and processing pipelines, classification workflows, and metadata structures for imaging datasets.
- **Part C – Microscopic Data:** Describes subcellular and high-content imaging approaches, data processing pipelines, and publishing procedures.

PART A - Genomic Data

1. Description of the Produced Genomic Data

1.1. Sample Provenance

- [TREC-Tara Europa](#) expeditions 2023–2024 (TREC Land-to-Sea Gradient: coastal & offshore waters, superficial sediments, Paleocores sediments, aerosols) for T1.1. and T1.2.
- Legacy/time-series observatories (Paleocores sediments - one core in T1.2, Time series Water T1.3,
- Seasonal land-sea gradients sediment and water T1.4,
- Seatizen biodiversity assessment water T1.5 (detailed data available in the future newly introduced Deliverable: D1.5 “*Update on Standardized sequencing and imaging data*”)
- Bioindicators of industrial impacts sediment, T5.1

1.2. Regions targeted/sequenced

- Metabarcoding (MetaB) is based on the targeted amplification of short genetic regions, uses a set of standardized markers (16S V4–V5, 18S V9, 18S V4, 18S V1–V2, COI, 12S Teleo and 12S Elasm). these markers, applied in whole or in part, depending on the biological matrices analysed, deliver a multidimensional characterization of biodiversity—from microorganisms to higher vertebrates—while ensuring broad taxonomic coverage, adequate resolution for the target groups. They also ensure compatibility of fragment sizes with Illumina sequencing platforms, and robustness in complex environmental samples.
- Metagenomics (MetaG) is primarily implemented through short-read Illumina sequencing, provides direct access—without any amplification step—to the full genetic potential of an environmental sample, thereby offering a comprehensive functional and taxonomic overview of microbial and unicellular eukaryotic communities.
- Metatranscriptomics (MetaT): based on Illumina sequencing of prokaryotic and eukaryotic transcripts (RNA), enables the assessment of the actual biological activity of communities, by detecting genes expressed *in situ* and revealing their functional responses to environmental conditions and pressures.

1.3. Data Deposition

- Primary deposition on BIOcean5D datahub; metadata submitted to BioSamples; raw reads submitted to ENA in private mode with progressive public release.
- timelines: data publication upon paper publication or (for TREC-related data) six months after release in the hub

2. Standardized Procedures

CEA-Genoscope performed end-to-end processing (from extraction to sequencing) for TREC samples originating from water, shallow water, sediment, and water eDNA (Figure 1).

For other sample types (T1.2/T1.4/T5.1.1 sediment, T1.3/T1.4/T1.5 water) partner laboratories carried out extraction and/or amplification (PCR) locally, then shipped labelled amplicon pools to Genoscope for library preparation and sequencing. Logsheets (PCR & pool) together with standardized labels were systematically used to register and track these shipments.

In addition, a subset of samples was processed and sequenced on other sequencing platforms outside CEA-Genoscope, depending on local expertise, specific project requirements, or logistical constraints. These datasets followed the same principles of metadata registration and BioSample ID traceability to ensure their integration into the central data flow and the Data Hub.

Figure 1: BIOcean5D Workflow – From Sampling to Data Submission.

2.1. Sampling protocols

Sampling followed the BIOcean5D handbook of protocols (D1.1: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11261905>) and was systematically accompanied by the recording of associated metadata.

2.2. Nucleic Acid Extraction

DNA/RNA extraction workflows varied by biological matrix. Extraction blanks were included in each sample processing batch. Low-biomass samples required specific handling to minimise contamination. A summary of the extraction protocols used across tasks is provided in Table 1.

Table 1: Summary of nucleic acid extraction methods across Tasks.

Task/Subtask	Biological Matrix	Nucleic acid purification short description	Processed by
Task 1.1 TREC gradients	Sediment	DNA/RNA co-extraction from 5g or 10g of soil using FecalSoil kit (Zymoresearch)	CEA-Genoscope
	Shallowater / Water	DNA/RNA co-extraction from 1 filter using Cryogrinding by Nucleospin purification (Qiagen)	CEA-Genoscope
	Aerosol, SML	DNA was extracted with a modified Powerwater DNA extraction kit (Qiagen). Samples were incubated (1.5 h incubation for SML, overnight for aerosols) in lysis buffer and proteinase-K heated to 60°C, followed by mechanical lysis with vortex and sonication. After lysis, inhibitors were removed, chaotropic agent was added and DNA isolation (Silica column for SML and Cytiva sera-mag select beads for aerosols).	ETH Zurich
	eDNA	eDNA isolation and purification using NucleoSpin eDNA Water kit (Macherey Nagel)	CEA-Genoscope

Task/Subtask	Biological Matrix	Nucleic acid purification short description	Processed by
Task 1.2 Paleocores	Sediment	ancient eDNA (MetaB) extracted with Quiagen DNeasy Power soil max, from about 10g of sediments,	IOPAN (extraction and amplification CEA-Genoscope (sequencing))
	Sediment	ancient eDNA (MetaG) Qiagen MagAttract PowerSoil Pro Kit from ≤ 200 mg	Univ. Copenhagen (extraction and sequencing)
Task 1.3 Time series	Water Plymouth	The majority of samples were extracted with the ZymoBIOMICS DNA Miniprep Kit (Zymo Research); 12 samples were extracted with the ZymoBIOMICS DNA/RNA Miniprep Kit (Zymo Research). Filter sections were added to 700 µl of kit lysis solution in kit lysis tubes, and were bead beaten three times for one minute duration at 10 m s ⁻¹ , with five-minute intervals on ice. From here, DNA extraction followed manufacturer's protocols with 100 µl final elution volume.	MBA, Plymouth
	Water Blanes	A lysozyme solution was added to the Sterivex cartridges containing the samples to lyse the cells. Subsequently, a second incubation with proteinase K was applied. DNA was extracted from the filters using a standard phenol–chloroform protocol, purified in Amicon Units (Millipore)	ICM-CSIC
	Water Banyuls	DNA extracted with Qiagen AllPrep kit after lysis with lysozyme, sds and proteinase K	CNRS-Banyuls
Task 1.4 Seasonal land-sea gradients	Water Roscoff	DNA/RNA co-extraction from 1 filter using cryogrinding and NucleoSpin RNAMini and Midi kits (Macherey-Nagel)	SBR, Roscoff
	Sediment Roscoff	For microflora analysis: DNeasy PowerMax Soil kit (Qiagen) from 10g of sediments	IFREMER Brest (extraction and amplification)
		For macrofauna analysis: DNA extraction from 5g of soil using FecalSoil kit (Zymoresearch)	SBR, Roscoff CEA-Genoscope (sequencing)
	Water Naples	DNA extracted from filters with Qiagen PureGene Cell and Tissue kit (Qiagen). RNA extracted with Qiagen RNAeasy PowerWater kit	SZN, Naples
Sediment Naples	For microflora analysis: DNeasy Power Soil Pro kit (Qiagen) from 10g of sediments	University of Naples (extraction)/IFREMER Brest (amplification) CEA-Genoscope (sequencing)	
Task 1.5 Seafloor biodiversity assessment	Water and Shallow water	DNA extraction using Quick-DNA Miniprep Plus Kit (Zymo Research)	SBR, Roscoff CEA-Genoscope (sequencing)

Task/Subtask	Biological Matrix	Nucleic acid purification short description	Processed by
Task 5.1.1 Bioindicators of industrial impacts	Sediment	DNA extraction using PowerMax Soil DNA Isolation Kit (QIAGEN)	NORCE/IO PAN
Task 5.1.3. Non-indigenous and invasive species indicators	eDNA	eDNA isolation and purification using NucleoSpin eDNA Water kit (Macherey Nalgen)	CEA-Genoscope

2.3. Quality Control (QC)

Quantification (e.g., Qubit/Nanodrop) and integrity checks (e.g., gel/Fragment Analyzer) were performed and can be provided upon request by the respective institutes that conducted the extractions. Samples with very low DNA quantity (<1ng) or RNA quantity (<30ng) or quality (degraded RNA) were excluded from processing.

2.4. PCR & Metabarcoding (MetaBarcoding Strategy)

2.4.1. Tasks 1.1 & T5.1.3, CEA-Genoscope

This protocols applies to:

- Task 1.1 TREC Land-to-Sea Gradients
- Task 5.1.3. Non-indigenous and invasive species indicators

Standardised metabarcoding targeted several genetic markers with optimised PCR conditions, including 16S rRNA V4-V5 (prokaryotes + eukaryotes), 18S V9/V1-V2/V4, COI, and 12S rRNA Teleo/Elasmo (Table 2). Each PCR primer pair was flanked by unique BID barcodes (Barcoded Identifiers) to allow secondary indexing. Up to 8-12 amplicons carrying different BID tags were pooled, thereby reducing library preparation and sequencing costs.

PCR reactions were performed in triplicate (or quadruplicate for COI), and each sequencing run systematically included two negative controls (Ultrapure Water). Positive controls were also amplified separately to validate PCR performance, but were not sequenced, in order to prevent contamination. Amplifications were carried out with Phusion High-Fidelity PCR Master Mix (Thermo Scientific, Ref. F-532L) for most markers, and with the Advantage 2 PCR Kit (Ozyme, Ref. 639206) for COI primers containing inosine bases.

DNA was diluted to approximately 5 ng/μl, and 10 ng total input was distributed per replicate PCR. For nested amplification, the first PCR product (e.g., 16S rRNA full-length with primers 27F/1492R) served as templates for the second amplification (e.g., 16S rRNA V4-V5 with primers 515F/926R), enabling recovery of prokaryotic amplicons from eukaryote-rich samples.

Thermal cycling conditions followed optimised programs for each marker (Table 2).

Following amplification, replicate PCRs were pooled and purified with AMPure XP beads (1.0× or 1.8× ratio depending on amplicon size). Purified amplicons were quantified using Qubit dsDNA HS assays and quality-checked by Agilent Bioanalyzer or equivalent. Amplicons were then normalised to 2 ng/μl, pooled (10–12 samples per pool, including one negative control), and shipped to CEA-Genoscope for library preparation and Illumina sequencing.

Table 2: PCR conditions for metabarcoding markers.

Marker / Region	Primer set	Amplicon size (bp)	Enzyme	PCR cycles	Annealing T (°C)	Purification	Notes	References
16S V4-V5	515F / 926R (Fuhrman)	~411 (prok), ~600 (euk)	Phusion HF	25	53	AMPure 1.0×	Nested PCR possible (FL 27F/1492R → V4-V5)	Parada, A. E., Needham, D. M. & Fuhrman, J. A. Every base matters: assessing small subunit rRNA primers for marine microbiomes with mock communities, time series and global field samples. <i>Environmental microbiology</i> 18, 1403-1414, doi:10.1111/1462-2920.13023 (2016).
16S FL (nested)	27F / 1492R → 515F / 926R	~1400 → 411-600	Phusion HF	20 PCR1 25 PCR2	53	AMPure 1.0×	Enables recovery of prokaryotic amplicons from euk-rich samples	Amann, R. I., Ludwig, W. & Schleifer, K. H. Phylogenetic Identification and in-Situ Detection of Individual Microbial-Cells without Cultivation. <i>Microbiological reviews</i> 59, 143-169, doi:10.1128/Mmbr.59.1.143-169.1995 (1995). Parada, A. E., Needham, D. M. & Fuhrman, J. A. Every base matters: assessing small subunit rRNA primers for marine microbiomes with mock communities, time series and global field samples. <i>Environmental microbiology</i> 18, 1403-1414, doi:10.1111/1462-2920.13023 (2016).
18S V9	1389F / 1510R	150-170	Phusion HF	25-40	57	AMPure 1.0×	Eukaryotic diversity	Amaral-Zettler, L. A., McCliment, E. A., Ducklow, H. W. & Huse, S. M. A method for studying protistan diversity using massively parallel sequencing of V9 hypervariable regions of small-subunit ribosomal RNA genes. <i>PLoS ONE</i> 4, e6372 (2009).
18S V4	TAREukF1 / TAREukR (V4f / V4r)	~380	Phusion HF	25-40	53	AMPure 1.0×	General eukaryotes	Stoeck, T., Bass, D., Nebel, M., Christen, R., Jones, M. D., Breiner, H. and Richards, T. A. (2010), Multiple marker parallel tag environmental DNA sequencing reveals a highly complex eukaryotic community in marine anoxic water. <i>Molecular Ecology</i> , 19: 21-31. doi:10.1111/j.1365-294X.2009.04480.x
18S V1V2	SSUF04 / SSURmod	~450	Phusion HF	20	55	AMPure 1.0×	Metazoan focus	Sinniger F, Pawlowski J, Harii S, Gooday AJ, Yamamoto H, Chevaldonné P, Cedhagen T, Carvalho G and Creer S (2016) Worldwide Analysis of Sedimentary DNA Reveals Major Gaps in Taxonomic Knowledge of Deep-Sea Benthos. <i>Front. Mar. Sci.</i> 3:92. doi: 10.3389/fmars.2016.00092

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Marker / Region	Primer set	Amplicon size (bp)	Enzyme	PCR cycles	Annealing T (°C)	Purification	Notes	References
COI	m1COIintF / jgHCO2198	~313	Advantage 2	16	45	AMPure 1.0×	Requires inosine-compatible enzyme	Leray, M. et al. A new versatile primer set targeting a short fragment of the mitochondrial COI region for metabarcoding metazoan diversity: application for characterizing coral reef fish gut contents. <i>Front. Zool.</i> 10, 34 (2013).
12S Teleo	Teleo04_F / Teleo04_R	~100–150	Phusion HF	25–30	48–53	AMPure 1.0×	Fish detection detection	Environmental DNA for Biodiversity Research and Monitoring, Pierre Taberlet, Aurélie Bonin, Lucie Zinger, Eric Coissac, Oxford Academic, 2018.
12S Elasmo	Elas02_F / Elas02_R						Elasmobranch detection	

2.4.2. Task 1.2: Paleocores - IFREMER, IOPAN and DTU

Extractions of ancient DNA were carried out in specific laboratories adapted and following specific procedures to avoid contamination with contemporary DNA (IOPAN for MetaB and University of Copenhagen for MetaG). For MetaB, amplifications were carried out using Phusion High-Fidelity PCR Master Mix (Thermo Scientific, Ref. F-532L) for 16S V4V5, 18S V9 and V4 markers on 3 replicates.

2.4.3. Task 1.3: Time series Banyuls - CNRS (OOB)

PCR reactions for the Banyuls long-term time series samples were performed in duplicate using high-fidelity Phusion Plus polymerase to ensure precise amplification and minimise errors.

2.4.4. Task 1.3: Time series Blanes - CSIC

The PCR reactions for the LTER Blanes Bay Microbial Observatory were carried out in a volume of 12.5 μ L, containing 1.25 μ L of template DNA, 0.5 μ M of the primers, 3.13 μ L of Supreme NZYtaq 2x Green Master Mix (NZYTech), and ultrapure water up to 12.5 μ L.

2.4.5. Task 1.3 Time series Plymouth - MBA

Template DNA quantification was estimated via Nanopdrop. Template aliquoting and amplification reaction set-up were conducted on different days, with full sterilization procedures conducted prior to and after each step, in the same vertical laminar flow hood. PCR products were purified with the GenElute™ 96 Well PCR Clean-Up Kit (vacuum manifold) to the manufacturer's instructions and eluted in 75 μ l of elution buffer. Quality of amplicons was assessed with the Agilent Bioanalyzer High Sensitivity DNA Kit; a sub-sample of 12 samples/controls per 96-well plate were assayed.

2.4.6. Task 1.4: Seasonal Land-to-Sea Gradients -water & sediment Roscoff - CNRS (SBR)

Amplifications were carried out with Phusion High-Fidelity PCR Master Mix (Thermo Scientific, Ref. F-532L) for 16S V4V5 and 18S V9 markers, and with the Advantage 2 PCR Kit (Ozyme, Ref. 639206) for COI (macrofauna).

2.4.7. Task 1.4: Seasonal Land-to-Sea Gradients - water Naples - SZN

Amplifications from Gulf of Naples were carried out with PrimeSTAR GXL Taq Polymerase (Takara Inc). All PCR reactions also performed extraction and PCR negative controls. PCR products were purified using AMPure XP beads (Beckman Coulter). Quality of amplicons was assessed with Agilent High Sensitivity DNA kit (Agilent). Quantity of amplicon was assessed using Qubit dsDNA HS Essay kit (Thermo Fisher Scientific)

2.4.8. Task 1.4: Seasonal Land-to-Sea Gradients - sediment - IFREMER

Amplifications from Roscoff and Naples sediment samples (microflora) were carried out with Phusion DNA polymerase (Thermo Scientific F-530L) for 16S V4V5.

2.4.9. Task 1.4: Seasonal Land-to-Sea Gradients - aerosols - ETH Zurich

Amplifications from ETH Zurich aerosol microbiome and field control samples were carried out with 2 x myTaq mastermix (Bioline, #BIO-25042) for 16S V4V5. All PCR reactions were accompanied with extraction and PCR positive and negative controls to identify contaminants.

2.4.10. Task 1.5: Seatizen science - CNRS (SBR)

Amplifications are performed using Phusion High-Fidelity PCR Master Mix (Thermo Scientific, ref. F-532L) for the 16S V4V5 and 18S V9 markers, and using the Advantage 2 PCR kit (Ozyme, ref. 639202) for COI.

2.4.11. Task 5.1: Sediment eukaryotes (foraminiferans and nematodes from aquaculture farms) - NORCE and IOPAN

Amplifications of the 18S V9 marker were performed using AmpliTaq Gold PCR buffer and polymerase (Thermo Scientific, ref. 4311806), including negative controls.

2.5. Library Preparation

2.5.1. T1.1, T1.2, T1.3, T1.4, T1.5, T5.1: CEA-Genoscope MetaBarcoding, Metagenomic

This protocols applies to:

- Task 1.1 TREC gradients (MetaB and MetaG)
- Task 1.2 Paleocores (MetaB)
- Task 1.3 Time series (MetaB on Water from Plymouth only and MetaG)
- Task 1.4 Seasonal land-sea gradients (MetaB and MetaG)
- Task 1.5 Seatizen biodiversity assessment (MetaB)
- Task 5.1.1 Bioindicators of industrial impacts (MetaB)
- Task 5.1.3. Non-indigenous and invasive species indicators (MetaB)

Libraries were prepared from purified PCR products or DNA samples using NEBNext modules with NextFlex adaptors. The quantities of material used as inputs have been defined according to the quantities available. End-repair, A-tailing, and adaptor ligation were automated on a Biomek FX (if high input) or done manually (if low input); ligated products were purified with AMPure XP; a post-ligation amplification (Kapa HiFi HotStart NGS Library Amplification Kit or NEBNext Ultra II Q5 Master Mix) was performed; libraries were quantified, normalised, and pooled.

Metatranscriptomic

This protocols applies to:

- Task 1.1 TREC gradients (MetaT)
- Task 1.4 Seasonal land-sea gradients (MetaT)

The strategies described below will be implemented between 2025 and 2026.

From totalRNA, different cDNA synthesis protocols will be applied to reduce off-target sequencing of ribosomal RNA (rRNA) reads. For samples dominated by eukaryotic material, methods including a poly(A)+ mRNA selection step will be used, which efficiently lower rRNA reads but exclude transcripts from prokaryotes. For prokaryotic RNA, a random priming strategy combined with rRNA depletion will be applied, enabling the synthesis of cDNA from both prokaryotic and eukaryotic mRNA as well as organellar transcripts. The total RNA yield could also be taken into account for selecting the appropriate cDNA synthesis method.

For **eukaryotic mRNA**, libraries will be generated using a stranded mRNA kit. Poly(A)+ transcripts will be selected, fragmented, converted to cDNA, and will be processed into directional libraries with indexed adaptors before PCR amplification and purification.

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For **bacterial and archaeal mRNA**, libraries will be prepared after rRNA depletion. A stranded RNA-seq kit using random priming and template switching enabled cDNA synthesis and direct library construction, with strand information preserved.

For eukaryotic mRNA, libraries will be prepared using the NEBNext Ultra II Directional RNA Library Prep Kit for Illumina with 50–100 ng of total RNA. Poly(A)+ RNA will be selected using oligo(dT) beads, fragmented by divalent cations at high temperature, and converted into first-strand cDNA with random hexamer priming. Second-strand synthesis will be performed, and the resulting double-stranded cDNA will be purified with a 1.8× SPRIselect clean-up (Beckman Coulter), end-repaired, and 3' adenylated. NEBNext Multiplex RNA barcoded adaptors (Illumina) will then be ligated, followed by a 1× AMPure XP clean-up. The ligated product will be amplified with 15 PCR cycles and purified again using 0.8× AMPure XP beads.

For bacterial and archaeal mRNA, libraries will be prepared with the SMARTer Stranded RNA-Seq Kit (Clontech/Takara Bio) after an initial rRNA depletion step with the Ribo-Zero Magnetic Kit for Bacteria (Epicentre). RNA will be chemically fragmented, and first-strand cDNA will be synthesised by random priming combined with SMART template switching technology. Single-stranded cDNA will then be directly amplified with oligonucleotides containing Illumina adaptors and index sequences, preserving strand information. RNA input quantities will vary from undetectable (Qubit) to 4 µg, requiring modifications of the depletion protocol for low-input samples. Depleted RNA will be concentrated to 10 µl using the RNA Clean & Concentrator-5 kit (ZymoResearch), following the procedure for retention of RNA fragments >17 nt. When total RNA input is ≥1 µg, 40 ng of depleted RNA will be used for cDNA synthesis, whereas for lower inputs, 7 µl of depleted RNA will be used directly. Single-stranded cDNA will be purified by two rounds of 1× AMPure XP bead clean-up, amplified by 18 PCR cycles using SeqAmp DNA polymerase and the Illumina Index Primer set, and the final library will be purified with 1× AMPure XP beads.

2.5.2. Task 1.3: Time series Banyuls - CNRS (OOB)

Metabarcoding:

A single round of PCR was done using "fusion primers" to add Illumina adaptors + indices for multiplexing.

2.5.3. Task 1.3: Time series Blanes - CSIC

Metabarcoding:

A two-step PCR approach was implemented to prepare the libraries for the LTER Blanes Bay Microbial Observatory. It involved the amplification of the target DNA region in the first PCR, followed by a second PCR to attach Illumina adaptors and unique indices for multiplexing. The oligonucleotide indices that are required for multiplexing different libraries in the same sequencing pool were attached in the second amplification step, carried out in a final volume of 25 µL, containing 2.5 µL of PCR product from the first

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amplification step, 1 μM of the dual-indexed primers, 6.25 μL of Supreme NZYTaQ 2x Green Master Mix (NZYTech), and ultrapure water up to 25 μL .

2.5.4. Task 1.4: Seasonal Land-to-Sea Gradients - ETH Zurich

Metabarcoding:

A two-step PCR approach was used to prepare libraries for airborne microbial communities. PCR library products were purified with Cytiva Sera-Mag Select beads (0.8 x and 0.7 x for PCR1 and PCR2 respectively) and adapters applied using Illumina Unique Dual Index primers. All libraries were quantified, normalised and pooled.

2.5.5. Task 5.1: Sediment eukaryotes (foraminiferans and nematodes from aquaculture farms) - NORCE and IOPAN

Libraries were constructed using the KAPA HyperPrep Kit (KAPA Biosystems, USA) and the KAPA UDI Adapter Kit 15 μM (KAPA Biosystems), following the manufacturer's instructions

2.6. Sequencing

2.6.1. Tasks 1.1, 1.2, 1.3, 1.4, T1.5, T5.1: CEA-Genoscope

This protocols applies to:

- Task 1.1 TREC gradients (MetaB, MetaG, MetaT)
- Task 1.2 Paleocores (MetaB)
- Task 1.3 Time series (MetaG)
- Task 1.4 Seasonal land-sea gradients (MetaB, MetaG, MetaT)
- Task 1.5 Seatizen biodiversity assessment (MetaB)
- Task 5.1.1 Bioindicators of industrial impacts (MetaB)
- Task 5.1.3. Non-indigenous and invasive species indicators (MetaB)

Sequencing was performed on an Illumina NovaSeq platform (SP/6000/X Plus flow cells) using paired-end modes of 2x150 bp or 2x250 bp, depending on the application.

Metabarcoding (MetaB): sequencing depth targeted 250,000 to 500,000 reads per sample, depending on the matrix complexity.

Metagenomics (MetaG, short-read): sequencing depth targeted 30 Gb per sample systematically.

Metatranscriptomics (MetaT): sequencing depth targeted 30 Gb per sample systematically.

This sequencing strategy ensured both standardised coverage across samples and sufficient depth to capture community diversity and functional potential across different sample types.

2.6.2. Task 1.1: TREC Aerosols - ETH Zurich

Airborne microbiome metabarcoding (metaB) sequencing was performed on an Illumina NextSeq 2000 platform with 2 x 300 bp XLEAP P2 chemistry in the Genome Engineering and Measurement Lab, ETH Zurich. Targeted sequencing depths were between 200K to 400K reads per sample.

2.6.3. Task 1.2: Metagenomics on Paleocores - UCPH

Sequencing was performed on NovaSeq 6000 S4 flowcell running 2x100 bp paired end (222 samples in total, total n. read 10.2 billions reads, range 9M - 105M reads, average 4.6M reads per sample)

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2.6.4. Task 1.3: Time series Banyuls - CNRS (OOB)

MetaB sequencing was performed on Illumina NextSeq 2000 with 300+300 bp XLEAP chemistry in a commercial laboratory.

2.6.5. Task 1.3: Time series Blanes - CSIC

MetaB sequencing was performed on an Illumina NovaSeq 6000 with 2 x 250 bp paired end in a commercial laboratory. A minimum of 50K reads per sample were sequenced.

2.6.6. Task 5.1: Sediment eukaryotes (foraminiferans and nematodes from aquaculture farms) - IOPAN and NORCE

Sequencing of forams and nematodes was performed on a NovaSeq 6000 instrument (Illumina, USA) in paired-end reading mode 2 x 300 cycles with Kit v1.5 (600 cycles) at the Center of New Technologies (CeNT, University of Warsaw, Poland).

2.7. Data Processing & Submission

Once sequencing was completed, the data followed a two-step processing and submission workflow.

At CEA-Genoscope, raw reads were demultiplexed, linked to their corresponding EBI-BioSample IDs (SAMEA identifiers), and subjected to initial quality checks. Negative and positive controls were thoroughly tracked throughout, and datasets were transferred in standardised formats and identifiers to ensure consistency across laboratories and sample types.

At EMBL Heidelberg, additional quality control was performed to verify sequencing depth, read quality, and sample traceability (e.g., mislabelling, sample swaps, or contamination). After validation, datasets were uploaded to ENA in private mode and simultaneously made available to the community via the TREC/BIOcean5D Data Hubs.

Within the Data Hub, sequencing files were integrated with harmonised metadata (including tracking information system) through their BioSample IDs, ensuring provenance and reproducibility. The platform also supported dataset versioning, metadata updates, visualisation of sample/site information, and batch download functionalities. In addition, sequencing datasets were cross-referenced with imaging and microscopy datasets, enabling integrated downstream analyses.

As for paleocore Metagenomic data (Task 1.2), raw sequences generated at the University of Copenhagen will be accessible via the BIOcean5D Data Hub, along with the associated metadata that will follow the guidelines defined in the Minimum Information about a Metagenomic Sequence (MIMS) checklist (Kottmann et al. 2008). This workflow ensured that all users accessed harmonised, traceable, and quality-controlled data, identical to what would later become publicly available through ENA.

3. Risks & actions

Budget and human resource constraints: Sequencing strategies were adjusted with input from all participating laboratories. Except for the samples from the TREC expedition (T1.1), DNA/RNA extractions and PCR were carried out locally in laboratories involved in the other

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Tasks in the different labs. Given the large number of TREC samples, their processing was prioritised in batches according to quality and quantity. A global rationalisation of sequencing strategies was also discussed (e.g., number of marker genes, sequencing depth).

Harmonisation across labs: Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs) and BID primers were distributed to reduce inter-lab variability; experiment plans and logsheets were validated by Genoscope prior to shipment.

Late sample shipments: Deadlines for receiving samples at Genoscope (amplicon pools, DNA, RNA) have been regularly revised and extended to ensure maximum coverage of all Tasks and completion of the project's objectives.

Sample quality/quantity issues: Some low-biomass samples fell below required thresholds. Whenever possible, alternative protocols (validated but less optimal) have been applied to allow further processing, despite insufficient material for standard procedures.

4. Current Status & Next Steps.

Status highlights:

- **TREC benchmarking** datasets produced: We carried out benchmarking on a small group of selected samples, testing different protocols – from extraction to short-read and long-read sequencing – as part of the MetaBGT strategies, in order to choose the best approach before applying it to all TREC samples
 - 2 DNA/RNA extraction protocols from sediment samples were compared
 - MetaB 16S/18S
 - MetaG/T short reads
 - MetaG long reads (on selected matrices)

Survey 1 (MetaB sequencing): Sequencing outputs for metabarcoding markers (16S, 18S, COI, 12S) are shown in **Table 3**, broken down by Task and sample type

Data are already available for a large subset of samples. The deadline for receiving the last remaining samples at CEA-Genoscope (as pooled amplicons) has been set for the end of November 2025.

Table 3: Overview of the metabarcoding sequencing outputs per Task, numbers in parenthesis are the ones that are still under preparation and will be available in the D1.5 which will update the datasets. Nb: number of samples. In blue are links to the datasets available on the data-hub at the time of publication.

Task	Biological Matrix	16SV4V5 Sample Nb	18SV9 Sample Nb	18SV4 Sample Nb	18SV1V2 Sample Nb	COI Sample Nb	12S Teleo Sample Nb	12S Elasm Sample Nb
Task 1.1 TREC gradients	Sediment	338	338					
	Shallow water / Water	277/552/ 43*	277/552/ 66*	/	/	/	/	/
	Aerosol/ SML	1386/296*	/	/	/	/	/	/
	eDNA	202	195	/	184	188	187	188
Task 1.2 Paleocores	Sediment	498	498	498	/	/	/	/
Task 1.3 Time series	Water Plymouth	0/560*	/	/	/	/	/	/
	Water Blanes	265	/	/	/	/	/	/
	Water Banyuls	448	/	/	/	/	/	/
Task 1.4 Seasonal land-sea gradients	Water Roscoff	0/204*	0/202*	/	/		/	/
	Sediment Roscoff	0/66*	/	/	/	0/102*	/	/
	Water Naples	0/206*	0/203*	/	/	0/178*	/	/
	Sediment Naples	0 (59*)	/	/	/	/	/	/
Task 1.5 Seaitizen biodiversity assessment	Water and Shallow water	0/2200 **	0/2200**	/	/	0/2200**	/	/
Task 5.1.1. Bioindicators of industrial impacts	Sediment	/	764	/	/	/	/	/
Task 5.1.3. Non-indigenous and invasive species indicators	eDNA	177	167	/	163	159	160	154

*The samples have been extracted, the PCR amplifications have been carried out or are still ongoing in the laboratories, and the sequencing has not yet been completed. Sequencing activities and availability of data on the DataHub are scheduled for 2026. The resulting sequences will be included in deliverable D1.5: “*Updated standardised sequencing and imaging data*”, which will provide an updated version of the dataset.

** The sample collection is currently underway and is expected to be completed by the end of 2026. At this stage, it is not yet possible to provide a projected date for the availability of the sequencing data.

Survey 2 (MetaG/T short reads): The current progress on metagenomic and metatranscriptomic sequencing is summarised in Table 4.

Several MetaG samples have been sequenced or are currently being sequenced. The deadline for receiving the last samples at CEA-Genoscope (as DNA or RNA) has been set for mid-December 2025.

Table 4: Metagenomic and metatranscriptomic sequencing status per Task. Nb: number of samples

Task	Biological Matrix	MetaG Sample Nb	MetaT Prokaryotes Sample Nb	MetaT Eukaryotes Sample Nb
Task 1.1 TREC gradients	Sediment	330	0/298*	/
	Shallow water / Water	332 / 571	0/293*	0/535***
Task 1.3 Time series	Water Blanes	0/132**	/	/
	Water Banyuls	151	/	/
Task 1.4 Seasonal land-sea gradients	Water Roscoff	0 (50**)	0 (50**)	/
	Sediment Roscoff	0 (62**)	/	/
	Water Naples	0/207** tbc	0/72 tbc**	0/216** tbc

* The samples have been extracted, library preparation are in progress and sequencing has not yet been completed. Sequencing activities and availability of data on the DataHub are scheduled for September-2026. The resulting sequences will be included in deliverable D1.5, which will provide an updated version of the dataset.

** The samples have been extracted but still in preparation for sequencing at

PART B - Quantitative imaging data

The marine part of [TREC](#) was carried out by the [Tara EUROPA expedition](#) (April 2023 – July 2024). Plankton – from microplankton (20 μm) to macroplankton (a few centimeters) – was sampled along European coasts (Figure 2-a). Microplankton was imaged using a FlowCam, and meso- to macroplankton using ZooScans (Figure 2-b). Images were acquired and/or processed, and identified at the [Quantitative Imaging Platform of Villefranche](#) (PIQv). In the following, we describe the successive steps: Tara Europa sampling (1), Data acquisition & processing (2) and Image classification (3), which were required to generate three available (4) quantitative imaging datasets: “Tara Europa WP2 20 μm - SUBSET”, “Tara Europa WP2 200 μm ” and “Tara Europa WP2 680 μm ”.

Figure 2. Tara Europa sampling effort and path (a) Size range (log₁₀ scale) of plankton samples, with associated sampling gear and quantitative imaging analyses performed for this project (b). Plankton icons ©planktomania.org.

1. Tara Europa sampling

Plankton was sampled during the daytime at 188 marine sites, divided into 15 legs along European coasts (Figure 3; Table 5). The sampling and storage protocols are available in the [D1.1-BIOcean5D sampling Handbook](#) (Sorbonne University & European Molecular Biology Laboratory, 2023). We summarise here the essential points to keep in mind for a good analysis and interpretation of the data.

Figure 3. Tara Europa sampling sites per leg. The start and end site of each leg is emphasized.

Table 5. Summary of Tara Europa legs with associated sampling sites and year.

Year	Leg	Name	Sites	Number of sites			
				Total	FCAM20	F200	F680
2023	01	Lorient → Spiekeroog	001 → 016	16	16	16	13
	02	Sylt North → Aarhus shore	017 → 024	8	8	8	8
	03	Samsø → Sopot offshore	025 → 033	9	9	9	9

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	04	Sopot pristine → Matsalu	034 → 041	8	8	8	8
	05	Tallinn Time Series → Kristineberg middle	042 → 058	17	17	17	14
	06	Kristineberg shore → River output Galway	059 → 076	18	18	18	18
	07	Bay of Brest → Bilbao shore	077 → 090	14	14	14	14
	08	Porto shore → Cadiz shore	091 → 099	9	9	9	9
2024	09	Marbella → Blanes	100 → 118	19	19	19	19
	10	Banyuls → Sète	119 → 121	3	3	3	3
	11	Rhône shore → Tevere shore	122 → 137	16	16	14	14
	12	Sarno shore → Villa Rosa	138 → 154	17	17	15	15
	13	Ancona → Neretva	155 → 166	12	12	11	12
	14	Kotor → Supersite Athens 5	167 → 178	12	12	12	12
	15	Arios estuary → Kavala	179 → 188	10	9	9	9
Total				188	187	182	177

1.1. Sampling onboard protocols

Plankton was sampled for imaging using three different types of nets, each equipped with a flowmeter. Owing to shallow depths, the majority of tows were conducted horizontally, though vertical and oblique tows were also undertaken where conditions permitted.

Microplankton was collected from *Tara*'s deck using a 20 µm decknet or overboard with a 20 µm WP2. These samples, intended for FlowCam analysis, were designated FCAM20 (see Handbook - Morphology – FCAM20 – FlowCam 4x). Each FCAM20 sample was passed through a 200 µm sieve to remove larger objects and prevent the flow cell from clogging. Samples were diluted or concentrated to achieve an optimal concentration for flow imaging (Figure 4).

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Meso- and macroplankton were sampled using a 200 µm WP2 net and a 680 µm Regent net, yielding F200 and F680 samples for ZooScan analysis, respectively. Both F200 (see Handbook - Morphology – F200 – ZooScan) and F680 (see Handbook - Morphology – F680 & F2000 – ZooScan) samples were concentrated on a 200 µm sieve. They were resuspended in 250 mL double-sealed bottles using filtered seawater saturated with sodium tetraborate decahydrate (borax), fixed with 30 mL of a non-buffered formalin solution, and stored at room temperature ($T > 10^{\circ}\text{C}$).

Figure 4. Onboard protocol for FlowCam samples. V: volume. Associated EcoTaxa fields are indicated in italics and in blue. Images from Mériguet et al., 2025 (credit Noan Le Bescot).

1.2. Sample summary

During the expedition, some plankton tows could not be performed due to various issues (e.g. bad weather, lack of time), resulting in missing samples (Table 5). At certain sites, high concentrations of gelatinous organisms caused clogging and prevented the nets from yielding quantitative results. These particularities are summarised in Tables 6–8 and Figure 5, and must be taken into account in the analyses. Please note that where sub-sampling has occurred (as indicated in the *sample_comment* data field), this has already been accounted for in the filtered volumes. Where sub-sampling does not apply to the entire sample, or where it is unclear, it has not been taken into account. The affected sites are listed in the tables below, with a ‘careful’ mention (e.g. site 157, Table 6).

Table 6. Summary of sites with missing or potentially non-quantitative F680 data.

Site	Category	Reason
001	missing	lack of time
003	careful	weird flowmeter start
006	missing	lack of time
010	missing	removed due to incoming bad weather need to pass Cap Cris Nez
011	not quantitative	big tear on Regent net
014	not quantitative	lot of gelatinous and polychaetes put in 500 ml to reduce but with very bad rinsing of sieve, cod and bucket
034	careful	the volume of the bottle was about 1500 mL but it was not precise (± 200 mL)

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Site	Category	Reason
051	missing	too much jellyfishes for the net broke cod end
052	missing	too much jellyfishes for the net
054	not quantitative	full of gelatinous organisms impossible to properly process
056	missing	lost sample
081	not quantitative	sieve clogged by gelatinous so subsample
083	not quantitative	too much biomass so subsample
123	careful	lot of velelle removed
124	careful	lot of salpida removed
128	missing	bad weather
133	missing	bad weather
134	careful	lots of crustaceans larvae which do not fit in the jar
141	missing	bad weather
143	missing	lack of time
157	careful	lot of gelatinous organisms huge bloom only 1/30 of them put in F680
158	careful	lot of fish larvae and gelatinous organisms 1/5 of them put in F680
182	missing	NA

Table 7. Summary of sites with missing or commented F200 data.

Site	Category	Reason
54	careful	gelatinous bloom filtration at 2mm
55	careful	gelatinous bloom filtration at 2mm
56	careful	gelatinous bloom filtration at 2mm
128	missing	bad weather
133	missing	bad weather
141	missing	bad weather
143	missing	lack of time
161	missing	lost collectors
182	missing	NA

Table 8. Summary of sites with missing or commented FCAM20 data.

Site	Category	Reason
005	careful	small leak in one of the window of the cod-end possibly not quantitative

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Site	Category	Reason
006	contamination	big black particle from the flow cell visible on the 200µm mesh
008	delay	run 7 hours after sampling
009	careful	weird flux on flowcell
020	image quality technical info	dirty flowcell red square area of the flowcell reajusted
026	technical info	flowcell change
028	contamination	few particles in the decknet with black particles from the tubing of the A40 pump
055	image quality	blurry images due to flowcell change
058	delay technical info	run 9 hours after sampling focus autocalibration procedure
077	contamination	The flowcell was cleaned with bleach a few days before this station and recalibrated. So some left calibration balls were in the samples
078	contamination	A kind of parasite upstreamed the flowcell so few pictures of one organism (= 'duplicate').
126	image quality contamination	New flowcell but very strange because very dirty and can't clean it, detritus are attached.
136	contamination	Black pieces of plastic/rubber particles from the A20 pump?
141	technical info	redlines alignment change
142	technical info potential contamination	autofocus calibration with beads before the run
179	missing	FlowCam HS
185	technical info	autofocus before the run
186	technical info	new flowcell, with autofocus made

Figure 5. Tara Europa sampling effort for A. FCAM20, B. F200 and C. F680 samples. Sites requiring special attention (because samples are missing, non-quantitative, or have a logsheet comment to bear in mind) are labelled, and detailed information can be found in Table 6, 7 and 8, respectively. Colour represents the total abundance of living organisms at the site.

1.3. Sampling metadata check and volume calculations

Coordinates from EcoTaxa exports, *Tara's* GPS and the BIOcean5D Data Hub were cross-compared to detect mismatches. Coordinates falling inland or far from the barycentre of the distribution were detected and curated. We chose to retain event coordinates from *Tara's* GPS; this approach relies upon accurate net deployment times. To ensure this, event coordinates that generated improbable tow distances or speeds were cross-referenced with, and corrected against, the vessel's logsheets.

Towing distances (*tow_distance_m*) were computed as the great-circle distances between the end and start of the geographic coordinates of the event, using the *geodist* function from the R package *gmt* (Magnusson, 2022; v.2.0.3). The duration of the tow was calculated from the recorded start and end times, which in turn enabled the calculation of *Tara's* speed during the tow.

Lacking cable angle data, we approximated oblique tows as vertical. Therefore, our calculation of theoretical filtered volumes considered only vertical and horizontal tows, as follows:

$$V_{theory_horizontal} = tow_distance_m \times sample_net_surf$$

$$V_{theory_vertical} = (sample_zmax - sample_zmin) \times sample_net_surf$$

Note that the fields *sample_zmax* and *sample_zmin* are not explicitly available in EcoTaxa .tsv exports for FlowCam samples.

Flowmeter-based volumes were calculated as follows. The 0.3 factor corresponds to the HYDRO-BIOS impeller pitch, and converts the number of revolutions into towing distance.

► F200 and F680

$$sample_tot_vol (m^3)$$

$$= (sample_flow_end_count - sample_flow_start_count) \times 0.3$$

$$\times sample_net_surf$$

Note that the fields *sample_flow_end_count* and *sample_flow_start_count* are not explicitly available in EcoTaxa .tsv exports for ZooScan samples.

► FCAM20 – WP2

$$sample_initial_col_vol_m3 = (sample_flow_end_count - sample_flow_start_count) \times 0.3 \times sample_net_surf$$

► FCAM20 – decknet

$$sample_initial_col_vol_m3 = (sample_flow_end_count - sample_flow_start_count)/1000$$

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The volumeter associated with the decknet directly counts the volume of water passing through in liters.

Net surface apertures are detailed in Table 9.

Table 9. Surface of the nets used during Tara Europa sampling.

Net	Sample_net_surf (m ²)
WP2–20µm	0.19625
WP2–200µm	0.25
RG–680µm	0.785

Theoretical and flowmeter-based filtered volumes were compared through linear regressions based on robust MM-estimates (Yohai, 1987; Koller and Stahel, 2011), using the *lmrob* function from the *robustbase* R package (Maechler et al., 2025; v.0.99-6). For the FCAM20 samples, as the decknet volumeter is highly reliable, only the volumes measured by the WP2 – 20µm flowmeter were compared to the theoretical volumes; this was for the 9 sites with vertical tows (Figure 6). This enabled us to detect and curate outliers due to metadata errors. After correction, the regressions suggest a good correlation between theory and measure for both F200 and F680 samples (Figure 7), with expected variability highlighting current effects and anchored sites, which were not accounted for. This gives us confidence in using the volumes measured by the flowmeters.

Figure 6. Comparison of theoretical and measured volumes from FCAM20 samples collected using vertical WP2–20µm tows. The dotted line marks the 1:1 ratio.

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Figure 7. Comparison of theoretical and measured volumes from F200 (left) and F680 (right) samples for each sampling site (in colour). Dotted lines mark the 1:1 ratio. Solid lines indicate the robust linear regressions, which account for outliers. F200 adjusted $R^2 = 0.67$; F680 adjusted $R^2 = 0.71$.

A problem was encountered for sixteen sites concerning F680 samples, where logsheets failed to indicate whether the Regent net had been used for F680 or S680-L samples. Lowest volumes were retained, which may potentially lead to an overestimation of the abundance. The difference is likely to be insignificant for the majority of sites; however, sites 004, 005, 050, 064, and especially site 084, require careful consideration (Figure 8). Information for both nets can be found in the Annex–Table A1.

Figure 8. Absolute percentage difference between the filtered volumes of both Regent nets measured by flowmeter. The solid line represents a 20% difference.

Finally, character fields were homogenised between FCAM20, F200 and F680 metadata for consistency.

2. Data acquisition & processing

Data acquisition and processing were carried out in two stages: samples of living microplankton from 20 to 200 μm (FCAM20) were imaged directly on board Tara using a FlowCam (Sieracki et al., 1998; 2.1), while mesoplankton (200 μm to 2 cm) and macroplankton (> 2 cm) samples (F200 and F680) were preserved in formaldehyde and later imaged using ZooScans (Gorsky et al., 2010; 2.2) at the Quantitative Imaging Platform of Villefranche (PIQv; Table 10). The ZooProcess software was used within ImageJ to process FlowCam and ZooScan images, extracting segmented objects as vignettes (Gorsky et al., 2010) and associating them with morphometric measurements (Picheral et al., 2017) related in particular to size (major and minor axes of the best-fitting ellipse, equivalent spherical diameter, area, perimeter), opacity (mean and median grey values) and shape (circularity, bilateral symmetry, elongation).

Table 10. Overview of the quantitative imaging processing operated on the Tara Europa plankton samples

Sample	Project	Instrument	Nb of scans (if relevant)	Total nb of images	Validated images
FCAM20	WP2 20 μm	FlowCam		1,106,692	100%
F200	WP2 200 μm	ZooScan	364	454,550	100%
F680	Regent 680 μm	ZooScan	177	188,025	100%

2.1. FlowCam – FCAM20

FCAM20 samples with optimised concentration (cf. 1.1; Figure 4) were imaged live using the “Autolmage mode” of an onboard colour FlowCam Cyano equipped with a $\times 4$ objective lens and a 300 μm flow cell. The detailed protocol is available in the BIOcean5D_D1.1_HandbookOfProtocols, section “Morphology – FCAM20 – FlowCam 4x”.

Updates to the ZooProcess software (version 8.18 and above) were specifically implemented to improve the processing of colour images and associate them with 98 morphometric measurements (note that most morphometrics such as size and shape-related ones are measured on the green channel). More than 4 million images were generated and imported into the EcoTaxa application for identification.

The classification of FCAM20 images by the PIQv corresponds to EMBRC request n°9965. The service was provided from 2025-01-07 to 2025-11-21.

To optimise the classification time while maximising the signal-to-noise ratio, the project was split into two fractions per sample (defined in the EcoTaxa field *process_subset_type*), based on the tests undertaken by Meriguet et al. (2025) resulting in induced errors of 0.02 % for the chosen thresholds:

- ‘high’: 100% of objects whose equivalent spherical diameter (ESD) > 44 μm (*process_subset_min_esd_μm*) were kept;

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- 'low': for objects with an ESD $\leq 44 \mu\text{m}$ (*process_subset_max_esd_μm*), 30 % were kept when there were less than 3,000 objects in the sample fraction. When there were more objects, only 3,000 objects were kept and the associated percentage was computed.

The percentage of the processed objects kept for each fraction can be found in the EcoTaxa field *process_subset_percent*. Note that the EcoTaxa field *object_esd* is in pixels; the field *process_pixel* (in μm) enabling the conversion from pixels to μm .

This resulted in 1,106,692 images to validate (Table 10), reducing the initial number of images by ~75 %.

2.2. ZooScan – F200 & F680

The process of F200 and F680 samples by the PIQv corresponds to EMBRC request n°9965. The service was provided from 2024-02-23 to 2025-08-15.

Formalin-preserved F200 and F680 samples were processed at the PIQv of the Institut de la Mer de Villefranche following a specific workflow (Figure 9). For each sample, the formaldehyde solution was replaced by filtered seawater under a hood (Figure 9-a).

F680 samples were passed through a 500 μm sieve and kept as a unique fraction 'tot'. F200 samples were passed through two successive sieves of 1,000 μm and 100 μm , to divide them into two size fractions 'd1' and 'd2', respectively (Figure 9-b). This ensures larger individuals are not under-represented, as they would otherwise become scarce when subsampled.

Each fraction, if needed, was subsampled using a Motoda splitter (Motoda, 1959) to reach a concentration of ~500–1,500 | ~1,000–2,500 objects per scan for F680 and F200-d1 | F200-d2, respectively. These limits were defined by the PIQv to minimise the overlap of plankton organisms while maximising the number of organisms for reliable quantitative measurements of the samples (Figure 9-c).

Subsamples were placed on the ZooScan's scanning tray. To enhance the imaging process, the organisms were manually isolated to favor a single organism per vignette. Each subsampled fraction was then scanned (Figure 9-d). Scans were processed using the ZooProcess software within ImageJ to extract segmented objects as vignettes (Gorsky et al., 2010) and associate them with 67 morphometric measurements (Picheral et al., 2017). A total 364 | 177 scans were carried out for the WP2 200 μm | Regent 680 μm project, resulting in 454,550 | 188,025 images generated, respectively (Table 10).

After each scan, quality controls were carried out to check the image quality and to ensure that the number of imaged objects are within the above-mentioned limits (Figure 9-e; see 2.3). If data did not pass the QC, the subsample had to be scanned again (Figure 9-d) or further subsampled (Figure 9-c).

Despite the care taken in manually separating the organisms on the ZooScan tray, some vignettes still contain several organisms (living and/or non-living); these are referred to as 'multiples'. Multiples have to be minimised because they are considered a single

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organism and are therefore unusable because they would bias abundance and size estimates as well as trouble classification. Multiples were manually detected and sorted in a distinct folder 'multiples_to_separate' (Figure 9-f). All vignettes contained in this folder can then be numerically separated by the analyst using a functionality of ZooProcess (Figure 9-g). Following this step, scans are re-processed and the quality control re-run (Figure 9-e).

After successfully passing the last quality control, processed data were ready to be imported into EcoTaxa, while re-conditioned samples were stored in the Collection Center for Plankton of Villefranche (CCPv; Figure 9-h).

Figure 9. Workflow for ZooScan processing at the lab, from the formalin-preserved sample to the processed data ready to import into EcoTaxa. QC: quality control. Image credit: Laëtitia Jalabert.

2.3. Details on quality controls

To ensure the quality of ZooScan quantitative imaging data, quality controls (QC) were systematically performed (Figure 9-e). The quality control tool for ZooScan data is accessible on the PIQv website: <https://sites.google.com/view/piqv/qc-tools/zqc> (last access: 17 September 2025).

Concerning acquisition, QC check the consistency of sieve values and spelling within the project, that the motoda has a valid numerical value and is logical when comparing scans of a given sample, and more importantly detect when the sample has been insufficiently or excessively split (assess motoda quality) by counting the number of vignettes generated. The limits are as follows: > 500 and < 1,500 vignettes per scan for F680 and F200-d1; > 1,000 and < 2,500 vignettes per scan for F200-d2. However, the coastal specificity of Tara Europa

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samples induce some challenges for quantitative imagery, such as lots of sticky algae rendering the separation difficult, high concentrations of fibers, small particles and detritus, presence of sand and seagrass, as well as gelatinous organisms disintegrating into smaller pieces. In some cases, the QC on motoda quality was therefore bypassed in favour of the living part of the sample, which was systematically justified in the *acq_scan_comment* field.

For processing, QC check that the scan is standard, has good image quality, and that its process created all the necessary files.

3. Image classification

Processed imaging data were imported into the EcoTaxa application (Figure 10). Three EcoTaxa projects were created, one for each sample type: FCAM20 → “Tara Europa WP2 20µm - SUBSET”, F200 → “Tara Europa WP2 200µm”, and F680 → “Tara Europa RG 680µm”. Artificial intelligence-assisted classification was performed by taxonomic experts from the PIQv (3.1). Cross-validation and quality checks were operated to ensure high-quality data (3.2). Morphological metrics were extracted through computer vision (3.3).

Figure 10. General workflow for EcoTaxa processing.

3.1. Taxonomic identification

Once imported into an EcoTaxa project, processed imaging data were automatically sorted into pre-defined categories (based on similar previous projects) using image recognition powered by semi-supervised machine learning methods implemented in EcoTaxa. This predicted classification was then reviewed by PIQv taxonomists for validation or correction. Note that “Tara Europa WP2 20µm - SUBSET”, as the PIQv’s first colour FlowCam project, necessitated a substantial upfront classification effort by taxonomists to train the prediction model.

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All images were classified into **taxonomic** (mostly genus level, sometimes species level) or **morphological categories**. The latter, designated 't00X', are temporary categories comprising objects of similar morphology where the taxonomy remains unknown. Unknown and rare objects are grouped into the 'othertocheck' category, which may contain a mixture of 'living' and 'not-living' objects. Vignettes containing 'multiples' that remain after the separation step are classified as either 'multiple other' (mixing 'living' and 'not-living' multiple objects) or 'multiple Copepoda', and are used for the final QC (see 2.3). The FlowCam-specific category 'duplicate' consolidates vignettes of unique organisms that were imaged more than once. Although technically classified under 'living', they should be considered FlowCam artefacts. The 'sphere' categories (small and large) gather spheric organisms that the FlowCam resolution is insufficient to identify accurately; consequently, these categories may include both 'living' and 'not-living' objects.

3.2. Final quality controls & error rate

Once all vignettes had been validated, each EcoTaxa project was subsequently retro-validated to ensure taxonomic consistency and to correct any misclassified images.

In the "Tara Europa WP2 200µm" and "Tara Europa RG 680µm" projects, all categories were fully cross-validated by at least two taxonomists, with the exception of the 'not-living' categories where 30 to 50% of the images were randomly checked, using an equal partition into three size classes. A final quality control on the number of 'multiples' was run (Figure 10). It assesses the effectiveness in separating 'multiples' by measuring three ratios in abundance and biovolume of the 'multiple other' and 'multiple Copepoda' categories in relation to the other categories:

- % ('multiple other' + 'multiple Copepoda') < 20 % of 'total living'
- % 'multiple other' < 15 % of ('total living' - 'Copepoda (with child)')
- % 'multiple Copepoda' < 15 % of 'total Copepoda (with child)'

If data do not pass the 'QC multiples', multiples have to be better sorted and separated again (Figure 9-f,g). If it still cannot pass after that, the sample has to be re-scanned (Figure 9-d) or even re-split (Figure 9-c).

For the "Tara Europa WP2 20µm - SUBSET" project, a different strategy was implemented due to the sheer volume of images: up to 300 vignettes per category were randomly selected (or all available vignettes if fewer than 300). These vignettes were simultaneously checked by two taxonomists to estimate the error rate. Only categories with an error rate greater than 15% underwent full retro-validation, after which the final error rate was re-estimated using the same methodology as previously described. The validation was considered complete once none of the categories showed an error rate higher than 15%. The resulting dataset achieves a global accuracy of 96.6% (weighted mean of taxonomic error rates = 3.4%).

3.3. EcoTaxa fields & concentration/biovolume calculations

EcoTaxa fields encompass sample metadata, acquisition and process information, and object metadata, annotation and measurements. All EcoTaxa field descriptions can be found in

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Picheral & Mériquet (2025; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15827159>). For Tara Europa projects, relevant sheets are “ZooScan” and “Flowcam_color_rgb_process”.

To come back to plankton *in situ* concentrations and compute biovolumes, here are the necessary fields and equations (more details can be found in instrument-specific manuals available on the PIQv website <https://sites.google.com/view/piqv/piqv-manuals/ecotaxaecopart-manuals>, last access: 17 September 2025):

- **Step 1:** Convert pixel variables into metric ones (take the square of the conversion factor for area variables)

FlowCam: $variable\ (pixel) \times process_pixel\ (\mu m)$

ZooScan: $variable\ (pixel) \times process_particle_pixel_size_mm$

- **Step 2:** Estimate the *in situ* concentration by taking into account all dilution or concentration steps for each sample (see Figure 4,9)

	EcoTaxa field	Unit	Description
classification	object_annotation_category	_	EcoTaxa category in which the vignette is sorted
V_{imaged}	process_all_frame_vol_ml	mL	Total volume processed by ZooProcess for FlowCam samples
$V_{optimised}$	sample_conc_vol_ml	mL	Concentrated or diluted water volume of FlowCam samples
$V_{filtered}$	sample_initial_col_vol_m3	m^3	Initial collected volume for FlowCam analysis, (if nets : sum of the nets)
	sample_tot_vol	m^3	Total filtered volume by the sampling gear for ZooScan analysis
subsample factor	process_subset_percent	_	Proportion (0 to 1) of the processed object kept for FlowCam subset
	acq_sub_part	_	Subsampling division factor of the sieved fraction of the ZooScan sample (1/x)

FlowCam:

$$concentration_in_sample\ (ind.\ m^{-1}) = Nb_{tot} / process_all_frame_vol_ml$$

$$concentration_in_sea\ (ind.\ m^{-3})$$

$$= concentration_in_sample \times \frac{sample_conc_vol_ml}{sample_initial_col_vol_m3}$$

▶ FCAM20

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$$\begin{aligned}
 Nb_{high} &= [Nb \text{ of organisms in object_annotation_category}]_{high} \\
 &\quad / \text{process_subset_percent}_{high} Nb_{low} \\
 &= [Nb \text{ of organisms in object_annotation_category}]_{low} \\
 &\quad / \text{process_subset_percent}_{low}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$Nb_{tot} = Nb_{high} + Nb_{low}$$

ZooScan:

$$\text{concentration_in_sea (ind. m}^{-3}\text{)} = Nb_{tot} / \text{sample_tot_vol}$$

► F680

$$Nb_{tot} = [Nb \text{ of organisms in object_annotation_category}] \times \text{acq_sub_part}$$

► F200

$$Nb_{d1} = [Nb \text{ of organisms in object_annotation_category}]_{d1} \times [\text{acq_sub_part}]_{d1}$$

$$Nb_{d2} = [Nb \text{ of organisms in object_annotation_category}]_{d2} \times [\text{acq_sub_part}]_{d2}$$

$$Nb_{tot} = Nb_{d1} + Nb_{d2}$$

- Step 3: Compute the biovolume (as a proxy of biomass) for each sample

FlowCam:

$$\text{Biovolume (mm}^3 \text{ m}^{-3}\text{)} = Bv$$

$$= \frac{V_{tot} \times \text{sample_conc_vol_ml}}{\text{process_all_frame_vol_ml} \times \text{sample_initial_col_vol_m3}}$$

► FCAM20

$$V_{high} = V_{high} / \text{process_subset_percent}_{high}$$

$$V_{low} = V_{low} / \text{process_subset_percent}_{low}$$

$$V_{tot} = V_{high} + V_{low}$$

ZooScan:

$$\text{Biovolume (mm}^3 \text{ m}^{-3}\text{)} = Bv = V_{tot} / \text{sample_tot_vol}$$

► F680

$$V_{tot} = V \times \text{acq_sub_part}$$

► F200

$$V_{d1} = V_{d1} \times [\text{acq_sub_part}]_{d1}$$

$$V_{d2} = V_{d2} \times [\text{acq_sub_part}]_{d2}$$

$$V_{tot} = V_{d1} + V_{d2}$$

▪ Plain biovolume:

Radius of a circle (mm) = r

$$= \sqrt{\left(\sum \text{object_area (mm}^2\text{) of object_annotation_category} / \pi \right)}$$

$$\text{Spherical Volume (mm}^3\text{)} = V = \frac{4}{3} \times \pi \times r^3$$

▪ **Riddled biovolume:**

Radius of a circle (mm) = r

$$= \sqrt{\left(\sum \text{object_area_exc (mm}^2\text{) of object_annotation_category} / \pi \right)}$$

$$\text{Spherical Volume (mm}^3\text{)} = V = \frac{4}{3} \times \pi \times r^3$$

▪ **Ellipsoide biovolume:**

Spherical Volume (mm³) = V

$$= \frac{4}{3} \times \pi \times \sum \left[\frac{(\text{object_major (mm)})}{2} \times \frac{(\text{object_minor (mm)})}{2} \right. \\ \left. \times \frac{(\text{object_minor (mm)})}{2} \right] \text{ of object_annotation_category}$$

4. Data availability

Quantitative imaging datasets from Tara Europa are currently available upon request via the EcoTaxa platform (4.1; note that metadata are always open access) and the BIOcean5D Data Hub (4.2) in a generic .tsv format. The datasets will be deposited in EMODnet in the coming months, and will therefore be accessible through OBIS and GBIF as well.

4.1. EcoTaxa

Quantitative imaging datasets are freely available on the EcoTaxa platform (Picheral et al., 2017) through the following path: Contribute to a project > Show other projects > Request access (Table 11).

4.2. Data Hub

The datasets are also available on the BIOcean5D datahub (<https://biocean5d.embl.de/index.cgi>) under the following names: “Tara-Europa-WP2-200µm-Zooscan”, “Tara-Europa-Régent-680µm-Zooscan” and “Tara-Europa-WP2-20µm-Flowcam”. The .tsv file corresponds to the general export of the Ecotaxa project.

Table 11. Summary of Tara Europa datasets and URL to access them.

Instrument	Net	EcoTaxa project name	Access	Authors
FlowCAM	WP2 20 µm decknet 20 µm	Tara Europa WP2 20µm - SUBSET	https://ecotaxa.obs-vlfr.fr/prj/15671	Marion Vilain, Victoria Bancel, Lisa Jeabert, Emmanuelle Martins, Anthéa Bourhis, Louis Caray-Council, Hugo Zaccomer, Olivier Bun, Karine Leblanc, Sophie Marro, Douglas Couet, Morgane Guillam, Marc Picheral, Laëtitia Jalabert, Manoela Brandão, Jean-Olivier Irisson, Fabien Lombard
ZooScan	WP2 200 µm	Tara Europa WP2 200µm	https://ecotaxa.obs-vlfr.fr/prj/11636	Marion Vilain, Victoria Bancel, Mathieu Atienzar, Camille Merland, Mélissa Tenaille, Anthéa Bourhis, Emeline Petit, Hugo Berrenger, Solène Motreuil, Denys Altukhov, Douglas Couet, Morgane Guillam, Emmanuelle Martins, Laëtitia Jalabert, Manoela Brandão, Jean-Olivier Irisson, Fabien Lombard
ZooScan	Regent 680 µm	Tara Europa RG 680µm	https://ecotaxa.obs-vlfr.fr/prj/11714	Marion Vilain, Victoria Bancel, Mathieu Atienzar, Mélissa Tenaille, Hugo Berrenger, Camille Merland, Lisa Jeabert, Olivier Bun, Anthéa Bourhis, Louis Caray-Council, Solène Motreuil, Emeline Petit, Denys Altukhov, Douglas Couet, Morgane Guillam, Emmanuelle Martins, Laëtitia Jalabert, Manoela Brandão, Jean-Olivier Irisson, Fabien Lombard

PART C - Microscopic data

Subcellular imaging of water samples of the [TREC \(TRaversing European Coastlines\) programme](#) was carried out by [EMBL's Advanced mobile laboratory](#). Plankton – between 5 and 500 μm – was sampled along European coasts (Figure 7). Images were acquired and/or processed directly in the mobile laboratory or at the [advanced light microscopy facility](#) at EMBL. In the following, we describe the successive steps: TREC plankton sampling (1), Data acquisition and processing (2) and publication of the subcellular imaging datasets (3): “TREC Live Plankton High-Content Fluorescence Microscopy Dataset” and “TREC Fixed Plankton High-Content Fluorescence Microscopy Dataset”.

1. TREC plankton sampling

1.1. TREC super site sampling

Plankton for live microscopy analysis was sampled repeatedly on multiple days at 7 marine stations at the European coastline, divided into 32 distinct marine sites (Fig.11a). A total number of 350 samples were collected by plankton tows either conducted on local boats at the indicated sites or on board the TARA schooner following the sampling protocols available in the [D1.1-BIOcean5D sampling Handbook](#) and transferred directly into EMBL's Advanced Mobile Laboratory, which was situated at the nearest harbor/marine institute. This enabled processing and live imaging of the samples within 4 h post sampling without further storage.

1.2. TREC regular sites sampling

Plankton for fixed microscopy analysis was sampled at 188 marine sites on board the TARA schooner and 112 shallow water sites along the European coastline (Fig. 11b). A total number of 600 samples were collected following the sampling and storage protocols available in the [D1.1-BIOcean5D sampling Handbook](#). The fixed samples were then transferred to EMBL's bio hub for further storage and analysis.

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Figure 11. TREC sampling sites accompanied by the Advanced Mobile Laboratory (a), and on board TARA as well as shallow water sampling sites (b). The numbers indicate several close-by sampling sites.

2. Data acquisition and processing

2.1. Confocal Live imaging

Multichannel confocal images have been acquired from 350 samples live in the advanced mobile laboratory during the TREC expedition 2023/24 (super sites). This allows one to study live in depth in a field context without fixation. The samples were processed and imaged as published in the [BioImageArchive submission](#). Briefly, confocal images were acquired in transmitted light and in 3 different fluorescence channels, capturing chlorophyll and phycoerythrin autofluorescence as well as staining for DNA or surface structures of the organisms. BioSamples IDs were mapped to the datasets in the data management system [LabID](#) at EMBL. The channel information was exported from CZI files and curated in LabID. CZI files were converted to OME-Zarr for cloud optimization and efficient data access across platforms by [EuBI-Bridge](#), kindly provided and supported by [EuroBioimaging](#). OME-Zarr files were compressed as ZIP. CZI image acquisition metadata was extracted into TSV files. These curated and transformed data are accessible via BioImage Archive ([S-BIAD2258](#)).

Additionally, the individual cells on each image have been segmented, individual PNGs have been extracted and matched with the corresponding sample metadata for EcoTaxa upload ([18361](#)). This has led to a total number of ~1 million objects ready for taxonomic annotation.

Figure 12. Confocal imaging and processing of live plankton samples. For each of the 350 live samples that have been processed and imaged in the advanced mobile laboratory during the TREC expedition, 50 tiles have been recorded (a). Each image contains multiple organisms with multichannel information about autofluorescence (red = Chlorophyll A, yellow = Phycoerythrin), DNA/surface staining with Hoechst (blue) and transmitted light (grey) (b). The images have been processed to the OME-Zarr standard, mapped with the sample metadata via BioSampleID and made accessible via BioImageArchive. Additionally the individual organisms were segmented from the images and uploaded to EcoTaxa for taxonomic annotation (c).

2.2. Confocal imaging of fixed samples

In order to extract subcellular features such as organelle volume and morphological variability, we developed a workflow for high-throughput, high-resolution, multi-color fluorescence confocal imaging by automated feedback microscopy (Fig. 13). The images are similar and compatible with the [eHCFM screen from the TARA oceans expedition](#), however, the workflow is significantly improved by automated feedback microscopy. This allows for: (1) Fast screen

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of significant number of organisms per sample (~ 1000) in low resolution. These images can be used for taxonomic classification and quantitative analysis of cell counts. (2) High resolution 3-D images of ~ 500 cells / sample. These images provide subcellular details and serve as a resource for quantitative analysis of organelle morphology and size. (3) Spectral unmixing of different fluorescent dyes and pigments allows the detection of more structures simultaneously.

Figure 13. Confocal imaging and processing of fixed plankton samples. 600 plankton samples have been collected and are stored in the TREC sample hub at EMBL. We developed a workflow to systematically process these samples, stain them with fluorescent dyes and image them on a confocal microscope. The online processing of the autofocus focus (AF) and LowZoom images allows targeted high resolution imaging of up to 500 objects per sample via feedback microscopy. The images will be processed in a post processing pipeline to spectrally unmix various fluorescent components and converted for publication to OME-Zarr image standard.

2.3. Processing of the images

Conversion to the new field standard image format OME-Zarr was performed that allows pan-platform compatibility of the data and sharing following the FAIR principles. Machine learning-based segmentation of individual objects allows feature extraction of 3D fluorescence data. These data will be a valuable resource for analysis of subcellular features such as organelles, interaction sites and morphological diversity.

3. Data publishing

The imagery database “TREC Live Plankton High-Content Fluorescence Microscopy Dataset” has been made publicly available as a public resource for taxonomy and subcellular morphology. It can be accessed via the following resources:

- 1) OME-Zarr versions of the original files on [BioImageArchive](#) submission S-BIAD2258
- 2) Browsable [OME-Zarr-versions of the scans on S3 buckets](#), which will be linked and visual inspectable through the BIOcean5D Datahub
- 3) ~1 million individual objects of on [EcoTaxa Project 18361](#)

4. Current Status & Next Steps

The development of the workflows to produce high content imaging data of **live samples** in the field and their processing is successfully concluded. We took special care to follow the FAIR principles and several rounds of data checks have been performed before the release of the data. With the publication of the images on the public repositories BioImageArchive and Ecotaxa the data are accessible to be analysed by all project partners and interested scientists worldwide. The data are thoroughly annotated to be AI-ready.

For the high-resolution imaging of the **fixed samples**, we invested additional time (6 months) in the development of an automated workflow that improves resolution and content to previously conducted fluorescence imaging screens.

In a first phase, the 300 fixed “FM20” samples from shallow waters and off shore sampling from the TREC expedition are imaged. Medium resolution images from >1000 objects per sample serve as quantitative, taxonomic resources, while >500 objects from each sample will be imaged in high resolution allowing to extract subcellular features and in depth analysis of natural pigments. Currently we have imaged 10 % of the FM20 samples and expect this task to be concluded in December 2026. We will provide a rolling submission of the data to BioImageArchive and Ecotaxa with the processing pipelines developed for the live dataset.

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Annexes

Table A1. Net specifications for the sixteen sites where F680 and S680-L nets are indistinguishable. The blue background indicates the currently chosen nets for F680 samples.

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Site	Date	Time start	Lat start	Lon start	Time end	Lat end	Lon end	Flow meter start	Flowmeter end	Sample_tot_vol (m ³)
2	2023-04-04	14:16	48.6994	-4.0733	14:26	48.6959	-4.0755	3014	4457	339.83
2	2023-04-04	14:43	48.6992	-4.0721	14:54	48.6954	-4.0746	4457	5791	314.16
4	2023-04-07	14:02	48.6693	-3.9389	14:32	48.6693	-3.9388	1499	3972	582.39
4	2023-04-07	14:39	48.6693	-3.9389	15:09	48.6693	-3.9389	3973	7270	776.44
5	2023-04-08	15:05	48.7138	-3.8642	15:25	48.7050	-3.8688	7274	10276	706.97
5	2023-04-08	15:30	48.7027	-3.8703	15:50	48.6934	-3.8705	10276	12477	518.34
9	2023-04-16	16:42	49.4654	-0.0887	16:47	49.4638	-0.0878	16658	17176	121.99
9	2023-04-16	16:54	49.4616	-0.0864	16:59	49.4604	-0.0853	17176	17642	109.74
32	2023-06-08	12:57	54.3275	11.7929	13:17	54.3245	11.8000	68995	70653	390.46
32	2023-06-08	13:25	54.3236	11.8024	13:45	54.3209	11.8088	70653	72447	422.49
33	2023-06-10	10:18	55.0851	19.0197	10:38	55.0761	19.0026	74753	78964	991.69
33	2023-06-10	10:54	55.0825	19.0143	11:14	55.0730	18.9974	78967	83053	962.25
35	2023-06-13	09:19	54.4061	18.9408	09:39	54.4043	18.9240	86886	90020	738.06
35	2023-06-13	10:02	54.4102	18.9539	10:22	54.4045	18.9423	90021	93444	806.12
47	2023-07-10	07:50	60.0791	22.2700	07:55	60.0811	22.2692	15569	16408	197.58
47	2023-07-10	08:06	60.0840	22.2685	08:11	60.0861	22.2679	16408	17235	194.76
50	2023-07-18	10:31	59.3341	18.1966	10:41	59.3348	18.1902	18316	19985	393.05
50	2023-07-18	10:52	59.3339	18.1942	11:12	59.3360	18.1831	19988	22396	567.08

D1.3 - Standardised sequencing and imaging data

55	2023-07-31	09:55	58.2570	11.3093	10:00	58.2602	11.3064	26262	27048	185.10
55	2023-07-31	10:12	58.2621	11.3056	10:17	58.2654	11.3027	27051	27820	181.10
62	2023-08-10	08:43	60.2640	5.1405	08:53	60.2612	5.1470	41401	42894	351.60
62	2023-08-10	09:12	60.2662	5.1388	09:23	60.2634	5.1463	42894	44649	413.30
64	2023-08-19	14:07	56.0401	-3.1155	14:10	56.0392	-3.1144	50071	50563	115.87
64	2023-08-19	14:38	56.0425	-3.1049	14:41	56.0429	-3.1073	50572	51328	178.04
84	2023-10-02	13:13	45.6604	-1.1576	13:18	45.6604	-1.1575	6523	6762	56.28
84	2023-10-02	14:50	45.6598	-1.1563	14:55	45.6598	-1.1560	6763	7748	231.97
86	2023-10-06	15:36	43.4164	-2.6888	15:47	43.4178	-2.6916	11234	13157	452.87
86	2023-10-06	15:53	43.4177	-2.6941	16:08	43.4200	-2.6878	13157	15266	496.67
91	2023-10-23	11:22	41.1332	-8.6832	NA	41.1350	-8.6826	36542	37531	232.91
91	2023-10-23	11:38	41.1339	-8.6824	11:47	41.1349	-8.6807	37531	38756	288.49
95	2023-11-05	15:29	37.1361	-7.4013	15:45	37.1391	-7.3947	56190	58046	437.09
95	2023-11-05	15:54	37.1352	-7.3961	16:09	37.1394	-7.3917	58046	59889	434.03

